

THE CONCEPT OF INDIC HEROINE AND PORTRAYAL OF SHAKUNTALA IN KALIDASA'S *ABHIJNANASAKUNTALA*

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Abstract :

Sanskrit Literature is ancient heritage of intrinsic value and aesthetic merit not only for India but for the world. It has achieved greatness in religion and philosophy which is largely due to its originality. Kalidasa is regarded as the greatest of all Sanskrit poets and playwrights of ancient India and his play *Abhijnanasakuntala* is considered to be a masterpiece. It received an overwhelming response in the West when it was translated to English by William Jones in 1789. The paper attempts to study the character of Shakuntala in *Abhijnanasakuntala* (through the translated English version by Arthur W. Ryder) in the light of Bharat Muni's description of a heroine in *Natya Shastra*. Sage Bharata, an ancient Indian theatrologist and musicologist, in his *Natya Shastra*, which is a treatise on Indian performing arts, describes a heroine in great detail. The role of heroine was generally considered to be subordinate to that of a hero in both Indian and Western classical drama and it is quite extraordinary for Kalidasa to have given centre stage to Shakuntala in his play replacing the hero as the protagonist and naming the play after its heroine. The paper attempts to establish the importance of a heroine in *nataka* by discussing the commentary in *Natya Shastra*. The paper also attempts to briefly analyse the heroines of the western classical drama and draw a comparison between Indic and Greek classical heroines.

Keywords: Classical Heroine, Sanskrit Literature, Natya Shastra

Introduction:

Sanskrit literature of ancient India is renowned universally for its originality, richness and aesthetic merits. The roots of Indian civilization can be traced in this ancient heritage which formed not only the language but also the religious and intellectual life and thought of its populace. Arthur A. Macdonell has rightly commented in his book *A History of Sanskrit Literature*:

“Among all the ancient literatures, that of India is, moreover, undoubtedly in its intrinsic value aesthetic merit second only to that of Greece.” (Macdonell, 1900)

The Sanskrit literature is extremely vast not only encompassing the Vedas, Upanishads, epics, drama and poetry but also criticism; the most extensive treatise on dramaturgy being the *Natya Shastra* by Bharata, who is greatly known for his theories on *Rasa* and *Bhava* in drama bearing some resemblance with Aristotle's *Poetics* in its theory of *imitation* and *catharsis*. One of the features that makes *Natya Shastra* different from *Poetics* is that it has dealt with the characteristics and attributes of a heroine or a female character in drama in great detail. Bharata wrote *Natya Shastra*, an ancient Indian discourse on theatre and its art, which covered every aspect of stagecraft where he emphasised the importance, role and function of a heroine in *Nataka* or drama. He described eight types of heroines calling them *ashta-nayika*:

- 1) *VasakasajjaNayika* -the heroine dressed up for union with her lover
- 2) *AbhisarikaNayika* - the heroine who secretly goes to meet her lover risking the storm, demons and the snakes at night
- 3) *Swadhinabhartrukanayika* - the heroine having her husband in subjection
- 4) *Kalahantaritanayika* - the heroine separated by quarrel
- 5) *Khanditanayika* - the enraged heroine who is "outraged by the audacity of her lover"
- 6) *Vipralabdhanayika* - the deceived heroine
- 7) *Virahokanthitanayika* - the heroine who bears the anguish of separation forever
- 8) *Proshitabhartrukanayika* – the heroine who awaits her lover impatiently.

The treatise deals with the emotions of heroines overcome with love, attachment and even hostility. Bharata categorizes them further into superior, middling and inferior and describes the four stages of their youth. He also discusses about the heroines who play the characters of chief queen and other queens, highborn wives and ordinary wives, concubines, artists, maidens and old dames. Such detailed analysis of a female character in *Natya Shastra* establishes the fact that heroines were considered important in drama like the heroes and they may not have been just a supporting character. However, the portrayal of a male character as the central figure of the play is common to both, Indian as well as the Western classical drama, where the story revolves around a powerful hero with heroines only as secondary characters. In such times, it was quite extraordinary for playwrights to portray a woman as the central figure and name their works after the heroines such as Kalidasa's *Abhijnanasakuntala*, Sophocles' *Antigone* and Euripides' *Medea*. The English translation of Kalidasa's *Abhijnanasakuntala* which is one of the finest Sanskrit drama, was greeted with enthusiasm by men such as Herder and Goethe in 1789 in Europe. Though we usually consider 18th century to be the period when the European countries gained access to the vast treasure of Sanskrit literature but Arthur A. Macdonell confirms that few European missionaries were already acquainted with the Sanskrit literature as early as 1651 when Abraham Roger translated the works of Sanskrit poet Bhartrihari into Dutch. The effect of Sanskrit literature on Europeans can be comprehended in the following comment by T.W. Rhys Davis in the introduction of the book- *A Short History of Indian Literature* by E. Horowitz:

“Some of the most influential leaders of Western thought, both in Europe and America, have considered that Indian thinkers, with a speculative vigour and originality following a natural line of development in isolation from the rest of the world, have succeeded in their views of life in grasping and emphasising certain phases of truth, religious and philosophical, that have been slurred over or not noticed at all in the West.” (Horowitz, 1907)

Natya Shastra's Concept of Indic Heroine

The art of criticism is one of the treasures of Indian classical literature and *Natya Shastra* takes the central place being the highest treatise on dramaturgy. The introduction of female characters in *nataka* according to *Natya Shastra* is quite interesting. It is first discussed in *Natyasastra* in the context of *Kaisikivritti*. The play produced by Bharata had only three styles (*vrttis*) - the Grand (*Sattvati*), the Energetic (*Arabhati*) and the Verbal (*Bharati*) and the theme was associated to warfare and combat, but Brahma felt that something vital was lacking. He felt that it was the feminine appeal that the play was lacking in. So, Brahma created nymphs from his mind for Bharata to complement his plays. Their association to the art provided the fourth *vritti*, the Graceful (*Kaisiki*). *Kaisiki* is connected with the erotic sentiments. It created an atmosphere of music, dance, romance incorporating lovely dresses and scenes etc. with women conducive to the erotic and comic sentiment. Thus, the four styles found place in classical Sanskrit drama.

Natya Shastra also reveals that Bharata gave similar status to a male and a female character in a play. In the English translation of *Natya Shastra* by Manmohan Ghosh (*The Natya Shastra: A Treatise on Hindu Dramaturgy and Histrionics*, 1959) chapter thirteen which discusses sitting postures and different gaits, takes in walking postures of women categorizing them further into young and aged, tribal, handmaid, half-women etc. Chapter nineteen which talks about modes of address and intonation, discusses how women must be addressed, again categorizing them as ascetics, goddesses, wives of senior persons, elderly women, king's wife, princess or a brahmin lady. When it discusses naming of warriors and merchants, it includes how to name king's wife, courtesan and handmaid as well. Bharata's a detailed account of the costumes, make-up and ornaments of male and female characters is discussed in chapter twenty-three. Chapter twenty-four which discusses basic representation, gives detailed account of feminine graces, physical graces, involuntary graces, beauty, charm, radiance and emotions of heroines. It is in this chapter where female characters have been categorised into divine, asura, gandharva, rakshasa, naga women etc. Chapter twenty-six talks about the efforts of men and women, women's movement of limbs, the jealous anger of women, men's sorrow & women's sorrow, men's fear and women's fear and women's intoxicated condition. Chapter thirty-four gives a detailed account of the types of characters and it discusses both superior and inferior male and female characters and four types of heroes and heroines. However, it is in chapter thirty-five which deals with the distribution of roles where Bharata talks about the suitability of women in certain roles, training for women in different roles, result of engaging women for acting, characteristics of a typical heroine and women who may be prohibited to be heroines.

While dealing with the specific qualities of heroine, Bharata says that in a drama the role of the heroine should be performed by a woman who owns the qualities like loveliness, upright nature, youth, charm, elegance, sweetness, skill to express, good voice with composed knowledge of *tala*, *laya* and sentiments. Such a comprehensive elucidation of the features, qualities, attributes and characteristics of a female character inestablishe that women were considered equally significant in a *nataka*.

Shakuntala – A true Indic Heroine

Kalidasa's play *Abhijnanasakuntala* can be effectively analysed in the light of the theatrical conventions compiled by Bharata in his *Natyashastra*. Kalidasa has inventively portrayed King Dushyanta and Shakuntala in vivid variety of images and metaphors. *Natya Shastra* articulates that depiction of both virtue and vice is significant in *nataka* as these rudiments, judiciously blended with others will produce *rasa*, which is the primary purpose of the *nataka* and *Abhijnanasakuntala* is a repository of countless *rasas*. Though the plot is simple moving from Dushyanta and Shakuntala falling in love, to their *gandharva* wedding, then their parting and lastly their reunion, Kalidasa has fashioned the charisma of Shakuntala in such a creative and inventive way that all the *bhava*s artistically incorporated and the corresponding *rasa* springs up to enthrall the spectators. These *SthayiBhava* or infusing stable sentiments according to *Natya Shastra* are *rati*(love), *hasa*(humor), *shoka*(sorrow), *krodha*(rage), *utsaha*(bravery), *bhaya*(terror), *jugupsa*(revulsion), and *vismaya*(wonder). The corresponding eight *Rasa* are *sringara*(passionate), *hasya*(amusing), *karuna*(pitiful), *raudra*(furious), *vira*(heroic), *bhayanaka*(dreadful), *bibhatsa*(offensive), and *adbhuta*(astounding).

We experience the *sringararasa* through the attraction, love and romantic desires of Shakuntala for king Dushyant and *karunarasa* during her departure from sage Kanva's hermitage separating her from her friends, her family and her home and during her rejection by king Dushyanta. The *raudrarasa* is experienced only once when the king questions Shakuntala's character in his forgetful state. The heroines in *natakas* are characterized by different stages according to the *Natya Shastra*. Some of the gesticulations of *Abhyantaraprakrti* who is under the effect of love, can be observed significantly in Shakuntala. She slightly reveals her smile, speaks gently with smiling downcast face, and tries to conceal her facial expressions. She passes through stages of love-lorn conditions described in the treatise before she finally unites with her husband. Kalidasa employed all these stages and created the erotic atmosphere through Shakuntala. The first stage which is *Abhilasa*, is presented as the pursuit for union after having recognized the lover influenced by longing and desire. We come across such indications by Shakuntala in ACT III where she confesses:

“Ever since I saw the good king who protects the pious grove -

I love him and it makes me feel like this.” (Ryder, 2005)

The second stage - *Chintana* may be illustrated by the thoughts or feelings of the heroine in tranquillity. The love song composed by Shakuntala on a lotus leaf in the same Act expresses thus:

*"I know not if I read your heart right;
Why, pitiless, do you distress me so?
I only know that longing day and night
Tosses my restless body to and fro,
That yearns for you, the source of all its woe."*(Ryder, 2005)

The other stages such as *Anusmrti* which includes despising of all other activities and sighing in memory of the beloved and *Jadata* when the heroine does not answer after being solicited, fails to hear or see things can be well interpreted in the Act IV when Shakuntala, lost in the thoughts of her lover, doesn't notice the arrival of sage Durvasas.

Bearing in mind the behaviour of the heroine, the *Natya Shastra* divides them into three types - *Uttama*, *Madyama* and *Adhama*. We can safely categorise Shakuntala as *Uttama* who displays the merits of a lady of superior nature who speaks only agreeable words even if angry. Her anger is also short - lived. It is in Act V, which stages Shakuntala's rejection, when we experience the *raudrarasa* for the first time however, it is vindicated by an appropriate cause:

"Wretch! You judge all this by your own false heart. Why would any other man do what you have done? To hide behind virtue, like a yawning well covered over with grass!"(Ryder, 2005)

As specified in *Natya Shastra* that noble man will be infatuated by the conduct, loveliness and upright character of the *Uttama* type of heroine, we very well see that king Dushyanta is fascinated thus towards Shakuntala. In Act II he describes Shakuntala's beauty to the *Vidusaka* in the following lines:

*"She is God's vision, of pure thought
Composed in his creative mind;
His reveries of beauty wrought
The peerless pearl of womankind
So plays my fancy when I see
How great is God, how lovely she"* (Ryder, 2005)

Such a gifted charm belongs to the *Uttama* type of heroine. *Natya Shastra* further pronounces that such a heroine will have proficiency in the art of love and will be unbiassed in her comportment. Kalidasa has depicted Shakuntala as an epitome of love. The spiritual and divine nature of her love is replicated in her attachment to the flora and fauna of the forest. Her love for the plants she waters every day is described as sisterly love and the wild fawn as her 'adopted son'. *Natyashastra* further says that gifted with grace and beauty she becomes annoyed when provoked though her speech will not suggest her mood. She could comprehend the reality of the matters and circumstances. We see that Shakuntala pardons Dushyanta upon knowing the truth behind her denunciation.

Considering Shakuntala as principal character in this play is not a mere extravagant statement. A critical analysis of the play establishes that Shakuntala is indeed the character who leads the story

ahead and even in her nonappearance on the stage, she lingers in the minds of the spectators constantly. Shakuntala's home, her surroundings, her character and beauty are presented by Kalidasa in the most illustrative fashion. Though Shakuntala never appears physically on the stage in Act II, Kalidasa never lets the spectators forget Shakuntala even for a moment. The whole conversation between the king and the *Vidusaka* in fact persuades the spectators to envision and perceive the divine beauty and youthfulness of Shakuntala in their imagination.

*"She seems a flower whose fragrance none has tasted,
A gem uncut by workman's tool,
A branch no desecrating hands have wasted,
Fresh honey, beautifully cool.
No man on earth deserves to taste her beauty,
Her blameless loveliness and worth,
Unless he has fulfilled man's perfect duty-
And is there such a one on earth?"* (Ryder, 2005)

It is in Act III where Kalidasa presents the love of Shakuntala and Dushyanta in the most erotic atmosphere which leaves the spectators awestruck in the ocean of *Sringararasa*. Act IV which deals with Shakuntala's departure from the hermitage is not much dissimilar from the traditional melodramatic *vidayi* of the bride we see even to this day in Indian weddings. The spectators get soaked in the *Karuna rasa* in watching Shakuntala leave her family, friends and her home to join her husband. Act V stages Shakuntala's rejection and her departure from Dushyanta's palace. From this scene onwards, the passage of time is hastened and time rolls forward in absence of Shakuntala who reappears only towards the end of the play. At this point one can question whether Shakuntala can be called the central character of the play? I will say yes because Kalidasa never allowed Shakuntala to leave the spectator's thoughts. He brought Shakuntala on stage through various devices such as her portrait, the signet ring gifted to her by the king and most significantly through the lamentations and grief of Dushyanta who could not forget Shakuntala:

*"No sooner did the darkness lift
That clouded memory's power,
Than the God of love prepared his bow
And shot the mango flower.
No sooner did the ring recall
My banished maiden dear,
No sooner do I vainly weep
For her, than spring is here."* (Ryder, 2005)

Heroine in Western Classical Drama

The origin of Western drama is traced in classical Greece, particularly in Athens where the theatrical culture produced three genres of drama: tragedy, comedy and satyr play. In his *Poetics*,

Aristotle has given utmost importance to *mythos* (plot) in Greek tragedy and has considered representation or spectacle to be less important but ancient Indian drama considered decoration (costume and make up) as an essential element. Manmohan Ghosh comments in *The Natya Shastra: A Treatise on Hindu Dramaturgy and Histrionics* (1959)

“Another peculiarity of Hindu dramas was their general dependence on dance (*nrtya*), song (*gita*), and instrumental music (*vadya*). Though the chorus of the Greek tragedy introduced in it some sort of dance and songs, the function of these elements seems to have been considerably different in the Hindu drama. The ancient Indian play was produced through words, gestures, postures, costumes, make-up, songs and dances of actors, and the instrumental music was played during the performance whenever necessary.” (Ghosh, 1959)

This signifies that singing, dancing and music were indispensable elements in ancient Indian drama and were accountable for creating a vital place for the heroines. *Natya Shastra* deals with every facet of ancient Indian dramaturgy discoursing both heroes and heroines almost similarly in a play, however it is problematic to find such elaborate philosophies in the Western classical literature but the heroines of Greek and Roman drama have become commendable archetypes. They are ardent women blessed with attractiveness, knowledge, intellect and valour however, they have no place in the society because they risked to cross the narrow frame of their time. In *A Guide to Ancient Greek Drama*, Ian C. Storey and Arlene Allan, while discussing about Aeschylus, an ancient Greek dramatist of the 5th century BC, establish that themes such as ‘women in love’ were never presented on stage in the ancient Greek drama, however, the theme of gender was used significantly and women have been given the role of men. In most of the Greek tragedies, heroines have been portrayed as women seeking revenge on the heroes, who breaks all the conventions of their time. Euripides’ *Medea* is a classic example in which Medea kills her own children ‘to spite her estranged husband’. Other themes that were employed to portray heroines in Greek drama were ‘seduction’ and ‘rescue’. In another play of his - *Ion*, Euripides explores the mental make-up of his heroine Kreousa and tries to understand why she performed the actions she did:

“mistreated by all the men in her life: raped and deserted by Apollo, her baby taken and brought up secretly at Delphi, married to a foreigner for political reasons, and who has not been able to conceive. What would such a woman be like after sixteen years, when she thinks that her husband will be reunited with a long-lost child, while she remains childless? What would such a proud woman do?” (Ian C. Storey, 2005)

Though Euripides seems to justify the actions of his heroines by presenting them in grave situations, still he portrays them as ones who are hated by God and by people. But he also presents them as characters who are important in the drama. They are depicted as sympathetic rather than villainous and he was the one to give a heroine, her important place in the Greek tragedy. In the play *Medea*, Euripides portrays a heroine torn between maternal love and her wish to take revenge, and she finally chooses revenge. In *Elektra*, he portrays Clytemnestra who did not waste ten years

conspiring vengeance for her daughter, but a woman who broke when her husband brought home another woman and acted out of frantic urge rather than planning.

The archetype of abandoned heroine is common not only in Greek or Roman drama but also in Indian classical drama. If we have heroines such as Dido - queen of Carthage abandoned by Aeneas, Medea abandoned by her husband or Ariadne abandoned by Theseus in Western classical drama, we have Shakuntala abandoned by king Dushyanta, Sita abandoned by Rama in Indian drama. In Ovid's didactic masterpiece, *Ars Amatoria*, the first two books are addressed to men but the third one is addressed to women and there are passages which distinctly speaks about the situation of women. It is difficult to find more treatise that talk about the heroines of ancient Greek and Roman drama.

Conclusion

After such an extensive reading, we may conclude that classical Indic heroines have been given a greater position in drama because of two reasons: *Natya Shastra* of ancient India but also because the western classical heroines have been portrayed as doomed women. Though they have been attributed with feminine and masculine qualities both, such as beauty, intelligence and valour but the ancient playwrights seem to support Aristotle's theory that such masculine characteristics are inappropriate for a woman and will lead to destruction. Though the heroines are virtuous but they are portrayed as driven by uncontrollable love or grief or pride or duty which finally leads to their ends. Dido is depicted as committing suicide by throwing herself on the pyre which she built to burn the belongings of Aeneas, driven by her excessive love for him and overcome by grief on being abandoned. Medea who has too much love for honour, this quality indeed attributed to great heroes like Achilles, kills her lover's new mistress and commits a homicide by killing her children as well for the sake of saving herself from being a laughter stock after her abandonment. For characters who have not been attributed with masculine qualities, are shown to be tragically weak to have continued their life in the absence of the hero. Ariadne, after being abandoned by Theseus on an island is crushed and frightened and goes almost mad.

The basic difference which decides the importance of a heroine in Indic or Western classical drama is the 'purpose' – why does these plays require female characters? While most of the Greek tragedy revolves around brave heroes who have a certain goal to achieve, encounter women in their life who bring romance and bliss but finally the heroes have to move on since duty was considered more important than love and hence leads to the idea that women are simply a part of the greater story, a supporting character. These women if given a centre stage, are portrayed as incomplete without heroes and their end as essential. The heroes, when they die, are depicted as dying in honour after exhibiting heroism, but the heroines, even if they are given the dominant role, are shown as dying tragically due to their excesses. The purpose is to attain catharsis and purgation by depicting the unhappy state of these heroes and heroines, but otherwise in both. When a hero dies, it is in glory and the play encourages the spectators to lead such a life of honour, but when a heroine dies, it

rather depicts the mistakes that should not be made in order to avoid such tragedies in real life. In ancient India, as already mentioned in the *Natyashastra*, the purpose of introducing women in drama was to add the graceful style along with the other four styles of drama, to bestow the spectators with the *Sringara rasa* and to add beauty, grace, romance, a celebrating environment of dance, song, colours etc. hence the Indic heroine's basic purpose is defined here- which is to bring feminine grace and charm to the drama. Brahma understood that the fourth *vritti* was equally important to complete true imitation of life in drama, which would have been incomplete if it was only about warfare and bravery. Also, since *Natyashastra* prohibits staging tragedies, Indic heroines do not suffer tragic deaths at the hands of the playwrights. At the same time, Indic heroines have been presented as epitome of virtue (rather than women failing to contain themselves) which defines their characters in grave situations such as separation from their lover and so the course of their actions is more or less predictable. They are seldom allowed to violate the codes or laws of the society by the playwrights unlike the Greek heroines.

Both Western and Indic classical heroines have merits of their own but what is worth contemplating is that it was quite extraordinary for the playwrights, be it of ancient India or Greece or Rome, to have

bestowed such individuality above everything else, to these heroines, to have given them such strong

sentiments of love or anger or grief and so creatively craft them that they compelled the spectators across the globe to gaze at them in awe without blinking an eye.

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